

Studies in Resin Catalysed Iodination of Some Aliphatic Ketones in Ethanol

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Iodination of some aliphatic ketones catalysed by hydrogen form of the resins Dowex-50W×8 and Amberlite IRC-50 has been studied in ethanolic solutions. The overall process obeys first order rate law. The rate is independent of iodine concentration, but dependent on the quantity of the resin or the hydrogen ion concentration in the resin phase. Process of stirring and its rate does not affect the rate of overall process of resin-catalysed iodination. Rates decrease with decreasing dielectric of the system studied by changing the solvent type. The effect of temperature on rate has also been studied and thermodynamic parameters evaluated. The rate controlling step in this heterogeneous process has been suggested to be the internal reaction at the site of the hydrogen ion in the resin matrix.

THE cation exchange resins in hydrogen form act as catalysts for a variety of acid-base catalysed reactions¹⁻⁴. Some of them, such as inversion of sucrose^{5,6}, ester hydrolysis⁷⁻¹² and esterification^{14,15} have been studied kinetically also. Bafna¹⁶ studied acetone-iodine reaction conductometrically in KI-free aqueous system using obviously very low iodine concentrations ($10.72 \times 10^{-4} M$).

In the present communication resin-catalysed iodination of three aliphatic ketones has been studied kinetically in ethanol medium using a strongly acid sulphonated polystyrene type exchanger (Dowex-50W×8) and a weakly acid carboxylic polymethacrylic exchanger (Amberlite IRC-50) in hydrogen forms.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

The resins used were conditioned with three cycles of regeneration and exhaustion as usual and were finally converted to hydrogen form, air dried ($\sim 20^\circ$) and stored. Exchange capacities were determined by standard methods¹.

All ketones were AR (BDH) chemicals. Resublimed iodine (BDH) was used to prepare always its fresh solutions in absolute ethanol. The strength of the solution was also checked by standardised sodium thiosulphate solution.

Reaction studies were carried out in three-necked pyrex flask (Cap. 250 ml) provided with an electrically operated stirrer having a glass stirring rod adjusted in the middle neck of the flask.

Rate studies :

The rate studies were carried out by using 50 ml of 0.05 N ethanolic iodine solution and required varying volumes of ketones with solvent ethanol to make the total reaction volume as 60 ml. The initial concentration of iodine in such solutions was predetermined in a stirred solution to which resin was added first, followed by a requisite volume of the ketone under study. The change in iodine concentration was noted by withdrawing 2 ml aliquots by momentarily stopping the stirrer (to avoid resin particles) at suitable time intervals and estimating it with sodium thiosulphate solution. For sharper end points these aliquots were diluted with water before titration.

Overall rate coefficients were calculated as k_1 (pseudo-first order rate constants) in all rate studies in ethanol as solvent involving variations in reactant concentration and resin quantity, H^+ concentration (Tables 1, 2,3). The effects of temperature (Table 4), solvent polarity (Table 5) and rates of stirring on reaction rates were also studied.

Results and Discussion

The rate data for the resin-catalysed iodination of ketones in ethanolic solutions has been found to fit in the first order rate equation. The rate coefficients, k_1 (Tables 1,2,3) increased with ketone concentration but were independent of iodine concentration. However, the plots of k_1 versus [Ketone], which were linear, did not pass through origin suggesting the involvement of some transition complex.

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF KETONE, IODINE AND H⁺ CONCENTRATIONS ON THE OVERALL RATE OF IODINATION OF ACETONE

Stirring rate ~1000 r.p.m. Temp. 25°C Resin : Dowex-50W × 8				
[Iodine] × 10 ³ , M	[Acetone] × 10 ³ , M	[H ⁺] in resin, M	k ₁ × 10 ³ , min ⁻¹	$\frac{k_1 \times 10^3}{[\text{Acetone}]}$
2.50	73.00	0.584	2.0	0.027
2.50	121.86	0.584	3.65	0.029
2.50	167.65	0.584	4.35	0.026
0.83	243.62	0.584	6.45	—
1.65	243.62	0.584	6.55	—
2.08	243.62	0.584	6.92	—
2.50	243.62	0.584	6.92	—
2.50	243.62	0.292	4.71	—
2.50	243.62	0.584	6.92	—
2.50	243.62	1.152	11.96	—
2.50	243.62	1.168	15.76	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF KETONE, IODINE AND H⁺ CONCENTRATIONS ON THE OVERALL RATE OF IODINATION OF METHYLETHYL KETONE

Stirring rate ~1000 r.p.m. Temp. 25°C Resin : Dowex-50W × 8				
[Iodine] × 10 ³ , M	[Me-Et Ketone] × 10 ³ , M	[H ⁺] in resin, M	k ₁ × 10 ³ , min ⁻¹	$\frac{k_1 \times 10^3}{[\text{Me-Et Ketone}]}$
2.50	20.00	1.168	4.61	0.235
2.50	40.00	1.168	9.29	0.232
2.50	60.00	1.168	12.01	0.202
2.50	70.00	1.168	14.30	0.243
1.66	60.00	1.168	12.72	—
2.00	60.00	1.168	12.61	—
2.50	60.00	1.168	12.30	—
3.30	60.00	1.168	12.40	—
2.50	40.00	1.168	9.29	—
2.50	40.00	1.460	9.41	—
2.50	40.00	1.752	11.24	—

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF KETONE, IODINE AND H⁺ CONCENTRATION ON THE OVERALL RATE OF IODINATION OF METHYL-ISOBUTYL KETONE

Stirring rate ~1000 r.p.m. Temp. 25°C Resin : Dowex-50W × 8				
[Iodine] × 10 ³ , M	[Me-i-But- Ketone] × 10 ³ , M	[H ⁺] in resin, M	k ₁ × 10 ³ , min ⁻¹	$\frac{k_1 \times 10^3}{[\text{Me-iso-But-Ketone}]}$
2.50	15.00	1.168	1.14	0.076
2.50	30.00	1.168	2.14	0.071
2.50	45.00	1.168	3.33	0.074
2.50	75.00	1.168	5.84	0.078
0.50	45.00	1.168	3.11	—
2.00	45.00	1.168	2.54	—
2.50	45.00	1.168	3.33	—
3.30	45.00	1.168	3.03	—
2.50	30.00	1.168	11.4	—
2.50	30.00	1.460	23.8	—
2.50	30.00	1.752	27.4	—

TABLE 4—[KETONE]=75.0 × 10⁻³ M; [IODINE]=2.5 × 10⁻² M
[H⁺] IN RESIN=1.68 M

Temp. °C	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹		
	Acetone	Me-Et-Ketone	Me-iso But. Ketone
25	14.9	12.3	5.47
30	20.4	16.6	6.99
35	31.4	21.1	8.12
40	40.6	28.1	12.60
45	58.0	37.2	15.90
E, K.cal.	12.80	10.50	10.07
A, min ⁻¹	5.95 × 10 ⁶	1.032 × 10 ⁴	2.100 × 10 ³
S*, e.u.	-29.5	-37.0	-45.0

The rates of resin catalysed reactions also increased with the resin quantity or the hydrogen ion concentration in the solid phase (Tables 1,2,3). The rates were found to be slower with a weakly acid-resin Amberlite IRC-50, as compared to those obtained with a strongly acid-resin Dowex-50 × 8 (Table 6). They also decreased with decreasing polarity (or dielectric constant) of the solvent system (Table 5).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF SOLVENT POLARITY ON RATE

Solvent	10 ³ × 1/D	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹		
		[Acetone] =73.0 × 10 ⁻³ , M	[Me-Et-Ketone] =70.0 × 10 ⁻³ , M	[Me-iso-But Ketone] =75.0 × 10 ⁻³ , M
Methanol	3.03	15.80	12.50	17.60
Ethanol	3.93	14.90	12.30	17.30
Dioxan	45.00	2.20	00.10	7.70
n-Hexane	52.09	0.58	00.63	6.00

TABLE 6—COMPARATIVE RATES OF IODINATION OF ACETONE WITH STRONGLY ACID AND WEAKLY ACID EXCHANGERS

[Iodine] × 10 ³ , M	[Acetone] × 10 ³ , M	k ₁ × 10 ³ , min ⁻¹	
		Dowex-50W × 8, 1 gm	Amberlite IRC-50, 2 gm
2.50	121.86	3.65	0.29
2.50	167.65	4.35	0.39
2.50	243.62	6.92	0.54

Superficially, the overall reaction appeared to be similar to homogeneous acid-catalysed halogenation of ketones^{17,18,19}. However, taking into consideration the heterogeneous nature of the resin catalysis, it can be said that reactants through diffusional processes enter first the liquid-solid interface and then the solid matrix to reach the sites of the ionisable hydrogens. The chemical reaction occurs there and is the same as in the homogeneous catalysis.

The rate controlling step can be determined by applying Helfferich criteria². The 'internal reaction' can be considered to be the rate controlling step in the present case as rates increased with catalyst concentration (Table 2). Stirring at different rates (i.e., at ~1000, 2500 and 4000 r.p.m) did not change the rates of reaction and hence film-diffusion as the rate controlling step was out of question.

A resin-ketone associated complex at the site of H⁺ ion in the matrix can be postulated as the first step in the process. This then undergoes decomposition and involves a slow rate controlling enolisation step involving a donor solvent molecule. Actual iodination is a fast step (cf. homogeneous acid-catalysed halogenation of ketones¹⁹). The high negative values of entropy of activation and comparatively low energy of activation (Table 4) suggest

the formation of some activated complex. The applicability of proposed mechanism for all the three ketones was confirmed by an isokinetic plot.

The increase of rates in more polar solvents (Table 5) were suggestive of the fact that the resin matrix loosened in such solvents due to swelling and made the H⁺ sites easily accessible to reactants.

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